

Identification of Future Commercial Grain Farmers: A Glaserian Grounded Theory Perspective

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In response to the call made in South Africa's National Development Plan 2030 to increase the number of commercial farmers primarily from the previously marginalised communities, this paper sought to fulfil that call by helping identify the characteristics of those farmers so that the cycle of food producers will not stop. A Glaserian grounded theory method was adopted for the study. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with fifteen grain farmers to explore the characteristics that help identify them. Participants included commercial farmers, emerging farmers, farmers whose businesses went under, as well as farm workers. Additionally, triangulation with three experts validated the characteristics raised by the participants. Findings showed that such characteristics would include scale of operation, independence, turnover and own or rented land. Thus, the practical implications are also stated as awakening policymakers and agriculturists to use the findings to identify and develop aspiring farmers. Regarding the theoretical value of the study, the uniqueness of the contribution mainly stems from the methodology employed (i.e., Glaserian grounded theory method).

Keywords: Future farmers, emerging farmers, commercial grain farmers, farmer characteristics, grounded theory

Building on McElwee's (2008) work on the taxonomy of entrepreneurial farmers, it is noteworthy to kick off the discussion by defining what commercial farming means. What needs to be clarified is the distinction between an entrepreneur and entrepreneurship where the first refers to the content of the phenomenon and the second to the process itself (Phelan, 2014). There are disagreements on the definitions of these two terms as they are evidently linked terms such as innovation, opportunity recognition, profit, economic growth, venture creation and change (Misra & Kumar, 2000). A further disagreement is regarding whether either of these two terms should be analysed at individual or organisational levels (Phelan, 2014).

Though entrepreneur as a term has continually been defined, re-defined, extended and re-interpreted for more than two centuries literature still lacks unanimity (Bull & Willard, 1993). Some definitions focus heavily on founding firms (Gartner, 1985) others focusing on opportunity as central to the definition (Shane & Venkataraman, 2000) while others focus on specific functional, individual and processual elements that underpin the conceptualisations offered (Omrane & Fayolle, 2011).

It is thus proper to start the review of literature discussing the approaches of studying entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship can be studied from various approaches, namely, trait, behavioural, opportunity and human capital perspectives.

Theoretical Background

Trait Theory

Studying entrepreneurship from the trait theory equips us with the

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knowledge that this theory is embedded in the personality theories and assumes that an enterprising individual is distinguishable from the masses by exhibiting specific personality traits (Phelan, 2014). In this vein, an entrepreneur is portrayed as a heroic figure within society seeking to identify the characteristics that distinguish the entrepreneur from 'mere mortals' (Ogbor, 2000). Literature on entrepreneurial traits mainly emphasises discussions on the "big three" as the need for achievement, locus of control and risk-taking propensity (Chell, 2008).

Need for Achievement (nAch)

David McClelland, the proponent of this theory of motivation which forms the cornerstone of the trait theory, advocated that the motivation to achieve is higher among entrepreneurs than the non-entrepreneurs. Phelan (2014) reports that a large body of empirical work tested and supported the nAch construct such as Fineman (1977), Johnson (1990), and Stewart and Roth (2007), while a sizeable chunk also contrast those findings by showing that nAch identifies a weak predictor of an individual's predisposition to start a venture (Hull et al., 1980), can just as easily be attributed to salespeople, professionals and managers (Low & MacMillan, 1988) and that a variety of push and pull factors influence the venture start-up intention (Chell, 2008). Consequently, literature remains divided regarding this issue even though the interest in it is still high.

Locus of Control

Rotter (1966) in Phelan (2014) came up with this other trait in one's personality, where a proposition is made in the dichotomy of one's belief. A belief that events occur within one's control refers to internal locus of control while such a belief that they occur outside of one's control refers to external locus of control. Rotter made a hypothesis that entrepreneurial career would be pursued by individuals with internal locus of control because of a desire to control their own destiny. On answering the question whether internal locus of control is the predictor of entrepreneurial careers, Kobia and Sikalich (2010) confirmed that many high achievers

exhibit high internal locus of control. Conversely, Chell (2008) found that research into locus of control as a personality characteristic that predicts entrepreneurial behaviour is by no means convincing.

Propensity for Risk

Within the trait theory, risk-taking propensity is central to the psychology of the individual entrepreneur and not just as an economic activity that he or she engages in (Phelan, 2014). This risk-taking element is best highlighted in entrepreneurship as it is defined based on its economic role. David McClelland's nAch work emphasises this role in the proposition that high achievers are predisposed to taking risks. Studies done by Hull et al. (1980) and Timmons (1994) support McClelland's proposition by showing that entrepreneurs do have a greater propensity to take risks, however, Stearns (1996) warns that successful entrepreneurs may as well be effective risk managers than the wild-eyed risk-takers.

Behavioural Approach

Unlike the trait theory discussed above that focuses on who the entrepreneur is, the behavioural approach focuses on what the entrepreneur does, that is the activities carried out by entrepreneurs. Phelan (2014) puts it well in an emphasis that this approach addresses entrepreneurship as it considers the set of activities and processes associated with the creation of a new venture.

Entrepreneurship as Venture Creation

Venture creation as the main entrepreneurial function is pioneered by Gartner's (1989) work in a seminal article 'Who is the entrepreneur? Is a wrong question' where an argument is presented that the creation of organisation distinguishes an entrepreneur from non-entrepreneurs. Davidsson (2003) states that Gartner's work laid the foundation on entrepreneurship research by revealing that entrepreneurship is about behaviour, rather than dispositions or characteristics; that it is a process; and that it is about emergence.

Though the behavioural approach is concerned with the actions of the entrepreneur, it does not neglect the individual and the individual behaviour because it is the necessary ingredient for venture creation (Phelan, 2014). This approach considers organisation as a primary level of analysis and the individual is viewed in terms of activities undertaken to enable the organisation to come into existence (Kobia & Sikalich, 2010).

Cognitive Processes

Cognition and cognitive psychology help to explain the mental processes within individuals as well as how they interact with the environment and the people. Cognitive processes refer to "all processes by which sensory input is transformed, reduced, elaborated, stored, recovered, and used" (Phelan, 2014, p. 73). Cognitive psychology has attracted many entrepreneurship scholars with a view to explaining how entrepreneurs think and behave (Mitchell et al., 2002; Katz & Shepherd, 2003; Baron, 2004; Grégoire et al., 2011; Sánchez et al., 2011). Entrepreneurial cognitions which are defined as knowledge structures people use to assess, judge and make decisions regarding opportunity recognition, venture creation and growth. It is through the cognitive approach that an entrepreneur pieces together information that helps to establish and grow a business (Mitchell et al., 2002). Phelan (2014) notes that elements of cognitive processes used to explain entrepreneurial

behaviour include self-efficacy, scripts, cognitive bias and opportunity recognition and are discussed below.

Self-efficacy

Self-efficacy in entrepreneurial behaviour aids in distinguishing between entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs as it explains why individuals of equal ability perform tasks differently. Entrepreneurs with high self-efficacy are able to identify opportunities, persevere any uncertainties and feel competent to overcome challenges (Phelan, 2014).

Scripts or Schema

Scripts or schema in entrepreneurship refer to the knowledge structures that people use in order to make assessments, judgements and make decisions whenever business opportunities arise as well as its creation and growth (Sánchez et al., 2011). These scripts are simplified models that entrepreneurs use to develop new products or services and to identify the resources for venture creation (Phelan, 2014). Entrepreneurial scripts are able to separate expert entrepreneurs from novice and non-entrepreneurs in that experts have refined knowledge about a particular domain that allows them to perform better in certain environments than others (Sánchez et al., 2011).

Cognitive Bias

According to Baron (2004), cognitive bias that may affect entrepreneurs includes optimistic bias, planning fallacy and affect infusion. Optimist bias refers to an inflated tendency to expect things to turn out well. Planning fallacy refers to a tendency to have a belief that more work can be completed within a given time than is possible, while affect infusion is the tendency for affective states to strongly influence perception and decisions. As a result, entrepreneurs' cognitive bias influences them to expect more favourable results than are practically justified on others.

Opportunity Recognition

Opportunity recognition within cognitive approach is studied from the perspective of understanding the perceptions. It has to do with object or pattern recognition and assumes that at some level opportunities exist as patterns or configurations of observable stimuli (Phelan, 2014). Our memories store the new patterns as they are distinctive from those readily stored. The stimuli may have distinctive features that include newness, practicality, novelty or uniqueness that the entrepreneur may recognise and then exploit. The assumption of the cognitive model is that through experience, prototypes of opportunities will form as mental abstractions which involve a comparison of ideas for new products or services with existing prototypes opportunity (Baron, 2004). The behavioural approach thus assumes that the entrepreneurial function ends once an organisation is created (Gartner, 1989).

Opportunity Identification Approach

Entrepreneurship basically comes into existence as a result of the identification of opportunities by entrepreneurs (Shane & Venkataraman, 2000). Nielsen and colleagues (2012) further argue that theory of entrepreneurship is made unique by focusing on opportunities. Below follows a discussion on the frequently cited key theorists in this area, namely Schumpeter and Kirzner (Phelan, 2014).

Schumpeterian and Kirznerian Opportunities

Schumpeterian theory proposes that opportunities arise through combinations of existing resources while Kirznerian theory assumes that opportunities arise resulting from the identification of gaps in the market and the use of existing market information (Phelan, 2014). As regards access to new information on entrepreneurial opportunities, Schumpeter held the view that changes in technology, political forces, regulation, social trends and macro-economic factors offered new information that entrepreneurs could use to recombine resources while Kirzner believed that entrepreneur should focus on optimising and making the existing market more effective. Kirznerian approach to entrepreneurial opportunity is considered not innovative as the focus is on replicating the existing information while Schumpeterian approach is innovative in that it focuses on emphasising new knowledge (Phelan, 2014).

The Individual and Opportunity

Shane (2003a) states that the opportunity identification approach here emphasises the individual's ability to exploit opportunities. Such an ability is affected by individual-level characteristics, some of which are psychological and others non-psychological in nature. On the non-psychological factors, entrepreneurs with experience coupled with a certain level of education are better at exploiting opportunities than those with lesser experience and education. Career experience is another factor playing a role here, as it reduces the uncertainty of an entrepreneur regarding the opportunity and the pursuit of profit.

Regarding the psychological factors, Shane (2003b) stresses the fact that they do not cause individuals to exploit opportunities, but they influence the exploitation decision. Psychological factors such as motivation, locus of control, vision, the desire for independence, passion and drive operate as general motivators, while goal setting and self-efficacy operate as task-specific motivators. Discussions on the previous approaches indicate that no single approach can be used to capture the true picture of understanding entrepreneurship (Kobia & Sikalieh, 2010). This now calls for additional body of literature that considers competencies as elements of entrepreneurial human capital (Phelan, 2014).

Having laid this theoretical background, it should be noted that a grounded theory study does base its foundation on any theory as theory forms part of the data. The purpose of this paper was to identify the personal characteristics of commercial grain farmers using a Glaserian or classic grounded theory method.

Method

As stated earlier, Glaserian grounded theory method was used in this investigation. Holton and Walsh (2017) offer three foundational pillars of classic grounded theory as emergence, constant comparative analysis and theoretical sampling. Emergence thus refers to the result of GT's open and exploratory stance in relation to the research field. Constant comparative analysis then refers to the process through which all data are analysed, as they are collected and together with all previously collected data. Theoretical sampling is the process through which empirical data are selected and collected as guided by the emerging theory.

Glaserian grounded theory uses two types of coding, i.e., substantive coding and theoretical coding, with the former preceding the latter. Hernandez and Andrews (2012) as well as Walker and

Myrick (2006) refer to the substantive coding as having sub-phases of open and selective coding.

The constant comparative process involves three types of comparisons, namely: incident to incident for the emergence of concepts, concepts to more incidents for further theoretical elaboration, saturation and densification of concepts, and concepts to concepts for their emergent theoretical integration and through theoretical coding (Evans, 2013). According to Hernandez (2009), the memoing process helps the researcher to determine which of the theoretical codes provides the best relational model to integrate substantive codes to theoretical codes. Finally, Evans (2013) states that theoretical saturation is achieved by the constant comparison of incidents in the data to elicit the properties and dimensions of each category or code.

In the current study, a total of about fifteen interviews with farmers, former farmers and farm workers. Triangulation with three agriculture experts was conducted to confirm the findings. Jane McPherson (personal communication on 2014, October 06) suggested the following criteria for choosing eight commercial grain farmers as suitable participants for this study:

- Had to be leasing or owning a farm.
- Farm location had access to travel and distribution infrastructure.
- Had developed the technical skills.
- Had ten or more permanent employees.

A further two participants who are farm managers were chosen based on the following criteria as suggested by McPherson:

- Had to be overseeing a leased or owned farm on behalf of the owner.
- Farm location had access to travel and distribution infrastructure.
- Had developed the technical skills.
- Had ten or more permanent employees.

According to Chaminuka et al. (2008, p. 368), "emerging farmers were defined as those previously disadvantaged farmers who are now participating in the market and are still facing some constraints to full participation." Ordinarily, these are the majority of Black African farmers falling in this category. So, for the purpose of this study, one participant who was classified as an emerging farmer (considered moderately successful) was chosen based on the following criteria, relying on the same sampling method as suggested by McPherson:

- Had to be leasing or owning a farm.
- Farm location had access to travel and distribution infrastructure.
- Had developed some technical skills.
- Had ten or fewer permanent employees.

An additional participant who was classified as a farmer who had a challenge that led the business stop operating (unsuccessful), was chosen based on the following criteria, relying on the same sampling method as suggested by McPherson:

- Had leased or owned a farm that is out of operation.
- Farm location had access to travel and distribution infrastructure.
- Had developed some technical skills.
- Had permanent employees in their payroll.

The participants' information was informed by reaching saturation, meaning that if gathered data repeats itself, further gathering of data would stop. As Bless et al. (2013) put it, using this method concentrates on getting information from the most extreme

cases, highly unusual manifestations of the researched phenomenon, obviously not representative of the target population, may sometimes be the most revealing cases.

Purposive sampling of about three experts from main grain suppliers for the selected farmers were chosen based on the following criteria as suggested by McPherson:

- Had ten years or more in the field.
- Had advised a chosen farmer for five years or more.

Furthermore, about two farm workers were selected following the purposive sampling method based on meeting the following criteria as suggested by McPherson:

- Had been employed permanently.
- Had been employed by the current farmer for ten years or more.

The purposive sampling of experts and farm workers serves as a strategy to include units that are judged to be the most common in the population in this investigation.

Ethical clearance to conduct this study was obtained from the University of the Free State in the Faculty of Economic and Management Sciences Ethics Committee on 01 September 2016. The ethics number is UFS-HSD2016/0133. Written informed consent was obtained from all individual participants involved in the study as the consent forms were signed. Confidentiality, privacy and anonymity were guaranteed to the participants.

Findings of the Study

This study took place in the province of the Free State, famously known in the farming sector as the breadbasket of the country. It is one of the nine provinces constituted in the Republic of South Africa. This province is demarcated into five district municipalities, which are: Thabo Mofutsanyana, Fezile Dabi, Xhariep, Motheo, and Lejweleputsa. The study was conducted in the district municipality of Thabo Mofutsanyana, which covers local municipalities such as Setsoto, Nketoana, Dihlabeng, Phumelela, and Maluti-a-Phofung. The focus was on Maluti-a-Phofung resulting from the fact that it was considered a poverty-stricken area by Statistics SA as it only had about 26% of employment with government being the major employer (Statistics SA, 2011). This municipality is in the eastern part of the province and borders both the province of Kwa-Zulu Natal and Lesotho. In this way, the weather patterns happening in both borders have a major impact in what happens in this area, such as the heavy winter snows in Lesotho and some big summer rainfalls in Kwa-Zulu Natal.

About fifteen farmers agreed to take part in the study, twelve of whom were male black and only three were male white South Africans whose ages ranged from 30 years to 74 years old. All the farmers were involved in mixed type of farming, which means that they plant crops and breed the livestock, especially cattle and sheep, except only one who was strictly in livestock. As shown in table 1 below, major grains planted in this district municipality are maize, dry-beans, sunflower, wheat and soya beans. Two participants do not own a farm but work on leased farms. Farm sizes for those who own them range from about 250 hectares to about just above 500 hectares. Additionally, the same table 1 displays positions of the participants on farms ranging from farmers themselves (farm owners) to farm managers (sons of farmers whose fathers were still very active on farm activities & decision making). About ten interviews were conducted in Sesotho except for two, where there was a mix of both Sesotho and English languages. Therefore, the tapes are recorded in

Table 1
Summarised Demographic Information of the Research Participants

2017-06-29	P1	Farm manager	35	Black Male	Age	After grade 12, did LADP Courses at a University	Race & Gender	Standard 8	Yes	Educational qualification	Real farmer	15 years	Are you a full-time bona fide farmer?	Number of years involved in farming	Family-owned farm	407 ha and 282 for grazing	Do you own a farm or is it leased?	Farm size	Home and on farm, home is 30 km away	Arable and grazing land	Live on farm or distance from home	There is livestock	Any livestock component on the farm?	Mixed farming but mainly producing crops	Type of farming	maize, soya, wheat dry beans & sunflower	Main crops planted	There are implements	Do you have own farm	How do you manage your farm implements?	Yes, sorted in that angle	Do you keep farming expenses records?	Yes, I am a member of AFASA	Are you a member of a farmer's organisation?	Do attend short courses offered by GrainSA	Are you part of any training and development programme?	What there a decline or increase in yield over the past three years?
2017-08-18	P2	Farmer	62	Black Male	Age	Standard 8	Yes	University	Since 1988	Are you a full-time bona fide farmer?	Own farm	250 ha	Do you own a farm or is it leased?	Number of years involved in farming	Family-owned farm	160 ha arable and the rest is grazing	Do you own a farm or is it leased?	Farm size	No but much of the time on farm, home is 20 km away & travel daily	Arable and grazing land	Live on farm or distance from home	There is livestock	Any livestock component on the farm?	Mixed farming but mainly crop farming	Type of farming	Maize, dry-beans, wheat & soya beans	Main crops planted	Yes, sorted in that angle	Do you have own farm	How do you manage your farm implements?	Yes	Do you keep farming expenses records?	Yes, I am a member of AFASA	Are you a member of a farmer's organisation?	Do attend short courses offered by GrainSA	Are you part of any training and development programme?	What there a decline or increase in yield over the past three years?

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2018-07-07	P3	Farmer	69	Black Male	No formal schooling	Yes	Since 1990	Own	360 ha	250 ha arable land and the rest is for Grazing	Sometimes but home is in Qwaqwa, distance is 15 km & travel daily	Yes, especially dairy cattle	Mixed farming, dairy and crop farming	Maize, beans and wheat and even soya	Yes, they have to be there	Around this time when we are done with the whole work, we look after them, fix everything, so that when rain comes you are not delayed by fixing them	Yes we keep them for tax purposes, and give them to book keepers	No these unions just take our money, we do not see what they do	There are GrainSA and Nestle for dairy	We did plant but drought hit us severely
2019-02-16	P4	Farm manager	30	Black Male	Grade 11	Yes, it is in my blood	I did this since I was nine years	Family-owned farm	408 ha		We live here on the farm	Yes, it is even dairy over there	Mixed farming, dairy and crop farming	We plant mainly beans, maize, soya, and even wheat	Yes	Like that one we use to harvest beans, after harvesting beans, we clean them up, take out the dirty stuff, apply oil	Yes, old man takes them to the auditors	I think is NAFU	I have been attending these workshops at NAMPO in Bothaville where these new Machines are introduced	The past three years yields were good except for 2018 where it was not good
2019-02-17	P5	Farmer	70	Black Male	Currently doing master's degree in agriculture	I can't say I am that much of a farmer. but as for work, i work even though i don't have land	Yea, it's been some time, sir. It's been 26 years now.	Well, as for work I but I lease land	400 ha	200 ha ploughed and about 150 ha though scattered for grazing	No, I travel about 60 km everyday	Sheep are somewhere far and the cattle in the different farms as well as fields in a different farm	Mixed farming but mainly crop farming	Maize, soya and beans	Yea, I do have the basic implements	I maintain them myself, I do it myself	It's a daily bread, you can't go without it	Many, many, many	I have done all the courses of GrainSA, all of them, 2017 was much better from scratch up to marketing	Last year was not that good, 2017 was much better. This year is going to be bad
2020-	P6	Farmer	60	White	Certif			Land	1600			Crops	Special	Yes	John Deere	Yes of	VKB			

02-26		Male	icatic in electri cal engine ering	on ha lease	only	ising in maize, sugar beans, soya & sunflower	does servicing of tractors & day to-day mainte nance done self	course, you can't control it, you can't manage it
2020- 20-26	P7 Farmer 74	Black Male	Standard 4		Mixed farming			
2020- 20-26	P8 Profes sional advisor /Expert	Black Male	Bachelor's degree in agriculture					
2020- 02-27	P9 Farmer	Late White 20's Male	Tertiary education		Mixed farming Livestock only			
2020- 02-27	P10 Farmer	Mid White 30's Male	Tertiary education		Mixed farming	Maize, beans, Soya, wheat		
2020- 02-27	P11 Farm worker	Mid Black 40's Male	Primary education		Mixed farming but mainly crops	Maize, beans, dry-beans, wheat & soya beans		
2020- 20-27	P12 Farm worker	Black Male	Matric	2002 work related but grew up on a farm	Mixed farming crops and dairy	maize, soya, wheat dry beans & sunflower	Did repairs	Used to attend courses offered by GrainSA
2020- 02-27	P13 Farmer whose business went under	Black Male	Former profes sional nurse	25 years own farm	Mixed farming crops and dairy	maize, soya, wheat dry beans & sunflower	There were implements	AFASA Attend courses at GrainSA
2020- 02-27	P14 Farmer	Black Male		Family -owned farm	Crop farming only	Maize, wheat, dry-beans, soya	There are implements manage them ourselves	Yes AFASA, VKB GrainSA
2020- 02-27	P15 Farmer	Black Male	Standard 9now grade 11	Since 2002 after my father passed on	Mixed farming	Maize, soya, beans	Have implements myself	Yes Nerpu member, VKB, AFASA and department of agriculture Organisation and rural VKB, AFASA development and Makholo Organisation

original language and only the transcripts contain translated texts. The remaining three were done in English. All the transcripts amounted to about 98 typed pages of text that emerged from the interviews. Every effort has been made to keep the richness of the information shared in the interviews, while for the interviews conducted in both languages, efforts of translation were only done on the Sesotho part, leaving the English one verbatim. The length of the interviews lasted from about 24 minutes to about 96 minutes. All the participants in this investigation were considered successful grain

farmers. They were categorised as such because of the recognition they received from GrainSA for producing high yields in certain crops such as maize.

Furthermore, Table 1 below summarises the demographic information of all research participants who voluntarily agreed to take part in this investigation. It displays their demographic information in the current study as told by themselves during the interview process that took place between the years 2017 and 2020.

Table 2

Selective Coding Theme: Defining a Commercial Grain Farmer

Sub-theme: Self-efficacy/Ability	
P2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Being commercial is reliant on the ability to produce food ● That will feed you as well as others, that is being commercial because you are able to eat and even sell; I produce, whatever I do I do with full force; When I want something I ensure its accomplishment, so receiving that title is informed by my expertise
P3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● But now when you are used to a thing, you cannot just let it go because of such. ● We can't just give in we have to tolerate this and move on. ● Never look back because even here is the community you need to hire them and pay them, move forward as a farmer, just move on and never give up as you will eventually achieve your goal ahead ● We are now used to working hard ● When the Lord permits we must just work hard and never look back, that is what we are used to, it is our burden, we can't do otherwise, it is unavoidable, it is our way of life
P7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Man, what I hear is that you are commercial if you are able to plant about 100 or 150 ha up to 200 ha ● Then if he has production there, then these agriculturists say if you are able to harvest that amount, you are classified as commercial that you refer to ● And move from the lower position.
P15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● No, I am not yet at the level of a commercial farmer but the way I think it is a person who is able to plant about 500 ha ● Commercial farmer is when you have enough implements, let me say perhaps you have about four or five tractors and you know that you do a particular thing at a particular time ● When you say you plant you do just that not that thing of using a ripper after that you come back to plant or spray, this one does this or you plant using three planters then you are commercial or you plant about six or seven farms even the cattle you have about 200 or more, even for your workers you have about ten of them who are permanent then you are commercial but at this moment we are still very low ● No it checks how much your work is able to cover ● It checks if your stuff is now fine, you no longer say I am going to hire, no you are now able to do all things by yourself, you no longer need any assistance even government assistance is not needed, like now as I say I want irrigation if you are commercial you only go to the bank and ask them to install whatever you like and you will pay, and you pay a certain amount annually. ● If you say borrow about R10 million they never doubt you ● Your assets are valued so much, if you say you want to buy this car ● They check what your security is should you fail
Sub-theme: Independence	
P3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● you see signs because there is no one helping you, you are on your own, are independent, you are not looking at anyone, there is no like government will take care of you, no, you are on your own ● There was Agriqwa where we received loans which we had to repay, they would help us that way but many could not survive but went under ● You can say you are commercial because you carry yourself, you need to know that if you want to do one two three, you should know how to do that, there is no one whom you would run to ● Yes, you stand for yourself, it will give tough time but you need to come up with plans on how to manoeuvre through that
Sub-theme: Commitment	
P3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● When you stumble and fall never say anything just rise and move on. Move on and say I am heading over there ● I arrived here, you know that, with just one tractor, a 165 Massey Ferguson, I will show you now, it bought all these other tractors ● It filled up all this space, when you hold on you move forward, never will you go back

P4

- Well for me what makes him stand out from other men would be his hard work

Sub-theme: Own or leased land

P5

- So the terms of reference from the minister said we need a commercial farmer to sit in that committee, then I was there before them and I said I am not a commercial farmer
- They said no you producing more than others, commercial farmer is not the question of producing to me, is a question of having land, I don't have land, so where do I commercialise my business
- Because I am seeing some challenges, first challenge is land, all the assets we have it, all the basic equipment we have them, all the basic implements I have them, all, all, all. So that's what I say, give me land, I won't go next door, just give me land
- Possession of the land
- Then you can qualify, then you can qualify
- So it might be continuous whether is it taken by the children, the grandchildren but that it stays in the family, it's sustainable, then I can call myself a commercial farmer. And they must work and produce
- That's how they even tell you when they sell the farm that it was in the hands of the family for the past sixty years
- It is still the same farm but running by the siblings of the farmer, working on the same farm, then you can say those people are sustainable
- When they come in you find that there are tractors, cattle, there's sheep, theirs is to maintain them and carry on

P6

- We haven't got our own farm. We rent from others.

P7

- Then they call you a commercial farmer but then they do not include things like tractors, whether you are using yours or hired that is not considered, they only consider that ability on a farm

Sub-theme: Turnover

P5

- So when it comes to turnover because they have a tendency of measuring commercialisation in terms of the turnover, yes I can qualify
- The turnover is the second question, yeah but you must have land first, but if you don't have land, working on contract basis, so can I call me myself a commercial farmer when contract expires in three years, the fourth year I don't have any land, am I still a farmer? I'm not, because I'll be out of business, I'm not, I'm not, that thing is not sustainable, it's not sustainable

P7

- The way I heard when we were at a certain place two of our people have achieved that and were raised to commercial as they managed to plant about 150 ha on maize which they succeeded

P8

- It doesn't matter, if a commercial farmer harvests 6 tons per ha
- And then if there is a possibility that a small farmer can also harvest the same yield even if he does not plough 1000 ha
- I think it will be fair to measure the performance of those two people

This study has shown that commercial farming is distinguishable from other levels of farming by mainly bearing four themes as displayed in Table 2 above, namely: scale of operation, independence, turnover and own or rented land. Each of these findings is presented below.

Scale of Operation

The production of food not only for oneself, but for the broader community, thus calls for intensive planning and come up with ways to carry it out. Being able to produce food in large scale has a lot to do with how much to yield per unit area, meaning that a defining factor here is the quantity of the yield. One research participant (P16) commented thus,

Another thing I cannot see here on commercial is that it survives on the scale of operation. So, if we define it as a large-scale farming operation but before we look at size someone with lots of money can do farming thinking that he is doing the right thing. I want this thing of the right thing to be a pillar of commercial farming because a lot of people do not do the right things. Someone may have a lot of money have large fields and big land but not doing the right things and that may cause his downfall in

farming, so that is not a commercial mind-set. A commercial mind-set must say you do the right thing, at the right time in a right place only.

Independence

Independence has to do with carrying out farming activities without relying on bodies, such as government assistance issuing grants or subsidies. In this regard, when a farmer decides, she or he should be able to stand by them and account for whatever the consequences they will come to bear. One research participant (P3) made this remark.

you see signs because there is no one helping you, you are on your own, are independent, you are not looking at anyone, there is no like government will take care of you, no, you are on your own.

Turnover

Turnover refers to the total output a business generates in a particular time. Thus, to be a commercial grain farmer, one needs to achieve a certain level of the output. Just as Table 2 showed, one research participant (P5) commented.

The turnover is the second question, yeah but you must have land first, but if you don't have land, working on contract basis, so can I call me myself a commercial farmer when contract expires in three years, the fourth year I don't have any land, am I still a farmer? I'm not, because I'll be out of business, I'm not, I'm not, that thing is not sustainable, it's not sustainable.

Another participant (P8) went further stating that

It doesn't matter, if a commercial farmer harvests 6 tons per ha. And then if there is a possibility that a small farmer can also harvest the same yield even if he does not plough 1000 ha. I think it will be fair to measure the performance of those two people.

Own or Rented Land

There must be a land available to plough the ground, either owned or on lease, where grain must be planted. Though there are those who advocate for land ownership, especially the previously disadvantaged group perceives this as a criterion to qualify as a commercial grain farmer, while their counterparts do not perceive it as a necessity. One research participant (P5) remarked

They said no you producing more than others, commercial farmer is not the question of producing to me, is a question of having land, I don't have land, so where do I commercialise my business.

As contained in Table 2 above, another participant (P6) brought out a different idea by stating that

We haven't got our own farm. We rent from others

while the other one (P7) confirmed this by saying

Then they call you a commercial farmer but then they do not include things like tractors, whether you are using yours or hired that is not considered, they only consider that ability on a farm.

Discussion of the Findings of the Study

Findings in the previous section address four themes, namely *scale of operation*, independence, turnover and own or rented land. Each paragraph below presents a discussion of these four themes.

Though not within the context of defining a farmer, this finding is consistent with McLean-Meynsse and Brown's (1994) research into the determinants of success for farmers. The finding of this study directs that a commercial grain farmer is identifiable by determining the scale of operation measurable by the yield per unit area and not the size of the farm.

Shane (2003b) states that psychological factors such as the desire for independence operate as general motivators. Lahiff and Cousins (2005) recommend that to graduate from smallholder to commercial farming, supporting smallholder farmers takes place at farm level through the provision of veterinary and agricultural extension services, research, mechanical services, credit facilities, transport services, development of irrigation and other infrastructure, training and market information. This level of support seems to be shrinking considerably once a farmer has become commercial in operation of the business as shown in the current study.

The finding regarding turnover in the current study defines how a commercial grain farmer can be identified. This finding is supported by Masika et al. (1998) where these researchers cite an example of the livestock commercial farmer who may aim to achieve faster growth, less mortality, coupled with high turnover which all translate into higher profits. Khapayi and Celliers (2016) concur that higher participation in remunerative agricultural commercial output markets defines commercial farming. There is little research if any

so far that can be used for the identification of commercial farmers in general.

Though the debate on land ownership is so important particularly among the previously disadvantaged South Africans, finding of this study accommodates both ownership and renting to commercialise farming. As far as these finding states, land is crucial for the sake of agricultural primary production. Khapayi and Celliers (2016) found that insufficient land availability to expand production limits emerging farmers from becoming commercial. Cousins (2009) contradicts this finding only in terms of the size of the land as smaller land is attributed to smallholder farming and bigger ones to the commercialised farmers.

Conclusion

Defining a commercial grain farmer is embedded upon the scale of operation whose defining factor here is the quantity of the yield and not the size of the operation. Independence refers to the ability to withstand the decisions a farmer takes as there is nobody to rely on for consequences. Turnover then relates to the ability to achieve a certain level of the output on the sale of the produce. Availability of land is of primary importance. The finding regarding land possession is not clear in the current study because it has shown that some farmers can commercialise their business without owning it but by leasing from others. So, these four factors are the main features that help to define a commercial grain farmer as proposed by this study.

In practice, the implications of this paper are twofold: first, policy makers would be able to use the findings to strategize on possible ways to lure aspiring farmers back to tilling the land. Second, agriculturists would be able to use the findings to identify and develop aspiring farmers so that food security remains with us forever.

It is noteworthy that the grounded theory research route is less travelled. Therefore, I do recommend that researchers consider adopting any methods within the grounded theory approach where formulation of typologies or frameworks would be realised particularly in the management studies. Besides this grounded theory approach, even mixed methods could be helpful in grounding the debate on the identification of commercial farmers in general.

Many previous studies have developed characteristics for different careers including some in the agricultural sector. However, very few if any have used the Glaserian grounded theory method to do the same to identify future prospective commercial farmers.

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